

Sm@rt project: Update on evaluation of innovative technologies by sheep and goat farmers

V. Giovanetti¹, M. Acciaro¹, A. McLaren², L. Grøva⁵, T. Keady⁴, B. McClearn⁴, L. Depuille³, R. Klein⁸, A. Godo⁷, P. Piirsalu⁶, C. Morgan-Davies²

¹ AGRIS Sardegna, Ricerca per la zootecnia, S.S.291 Km 18,600, 07100 Sassari, Italy, ² SRUC, West Mains road, EH9 3JG Edinburgh, United Kingdom, ³ IDELE, Campus INRAe, 31321 Castanet Tolosan, France, ⁴ Teagasc, Mellows Campus, H65 R718 Athenry, Co. Galway, Ireland, ⁵ NIBIO, Gunners veg 6, 6630 Tingvoll, Norway, ⁶ EULS, Fr.R. Kreutzwaldi 1, 51006 Tartu, Estonia, ⁷ ARO, The Volcani Centre, 7505101 Rishon LeTsiyon, Israel, ⁸ UNIDEB, Egyetem Ter 1, 4032 Debrecen, Hungary

Sm@RT (Sm@ll Ruminant Technology) is a EU Horizon 2020 funded thematic network, involving 8 countries, aiming at encouraging the uptake of technology on small ruminant farms. The best innovative technologies were selected in each country and evaluated by sheep and goat farmers at 2 different levels: Training sessions (Digifarms, research center), from researchers to farmers, and Demonstration days (Innovative Farms, commercial farms), from farmer to farmer, in order to provide tangible knowhow on practice and to allow the farmers to see, experience and understand in practice how the different technologies work on farms. Farmers attending the events completed questionnaires before and after evaluating a technology, to gauge if their opinions changed after the sessions. During these events, the cost benefit analysis of technologies was also presented. The results and feedback of farmers' evaluations were summarized for each country. For some technology, farmer's opinion changed after the training. For most of the technologies evaluated, farmers thought that was worth investing and implementing them on their farms, probably for the moderate to high levels of practicality and economic value detected. Knowledge sharing from farmer to farmer in commercial farms has been a success. Digifarms remain a reference point for farmers who need to improve their knowledge of a specific technology